

Influence of Religious Leaders on the adoption of Media Cholera-Related Awareness Campaigns in Atiba Local Government Area of Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the roles of religious leaders on the adoption of media cholera-related awareness campaigns in Atiba Local Government area. The study adopted a mixed method. Survey and in-depth interview methods were adopted to guide the study. Findings showed that religious leaders are very influential in the adoption of media cholera-related awareness campaigns on radio because religious leaders are more trusted and have higher credibility. Findings also showed that community engagement and mobilisation have minimised the effects of cholera through water sanitation and hygienic practices. It was, therefore, recommended that unlike the media of communication that are urban-centric and disseminate health-related messages to the people in the urban

centres, religious leaders must be used for health-related information such as cholera awareness programmes and knowledge in local communities. Women, men, young boys and girls must be made to participate in the initiation anti-cholera campaigns, prevention, management and control to fight against perennial cases of cholera disease in local communities in Atiba Local Government Area and even urban centres.

Keywords: Religious Leaders, Media, Awareness, Campaigns, Cholera

Introduction

Africa continent accounts for 94% cases of cholera worldwide (Guerra, Mayana, Djibo, Manzo, Llosa & Grais, 2012). Cholera is a major cause of mortality and morbidity among children under the age of five years. Cholera is caused by vibrio cholerae and it is very dangerous and infectious disease that requires instant medical attention (Fitria, Hasanah, Subchan & Pratama, 2019). The interdependent relationship between health and sanitation has been noted in many health studies. Cholera is the major disease associated with poor sanitation and unhygienic practices in sub-Saharan Africa (Prah, 2018). Perennial outbreaks of cholera in Nigeria grab the media attention all over the world. Religious leaders are the most credible medium of community-based campaigns in Africa. Religious leaders in Africa custody many people who follow them and perceive the religious leaders to be more credible and trustworthy. Cholera is a public health concern in most developing nations, where the issues of good hygienic practices, sanitation, clean and safe drinking water have remained a recurring issue. Global statistics shows that cholera infects 2.5 million people yearly of which 0.14 million people die as a result of absence of timely provision of appropriate treatment (Shrivastava & Shrivastava, 2020). Since year 2005, the outbreak of cholera has been persistent and more countries report the outbreak and menace of cholera to the World Health Organisation every year. Poor sanitation, unclean water supply and consumption, poor health literacy and absence of community mobilisation and poor national plans to arrest the perennial outbreaks of the disease have been the major reasons why the disease has kept recurring in most endemic nations. The disease affects the poorest and the most vulnerable individuals in developing nations as a result of unhygienic practices. A study conducted by Estrada, Argandoña, Hernández, Miranda, Gutierrez, Montalvo & Vega (2023) showed that contaminated drinking water and poor sanitation practices are causal factors for the transmission of diseases such as cholera, dysentery and diarrhoea.

Statement of the Problem

Religious leaders have been found to play a crucial role in mobilising and enlightening their followers on certain health behaviour. Religious leaders have been identified to be effective in the religious dominated areas, especially when it comes to western public health programmes (Walker, Hashim & Oranye, 2019). There have been reports of deep-seated suspicions of public health programmes especially when the traditional rulers and religious leaders are left out of such public health interventions. Religious leaders adopt the most effective channels to reach every member of the sect and persuade them to

embrace the health intervention programme by the local or international agencies or government (Nkwam-Uwaoma, Ojiakor & Onovo, 2019). Religious leaders are more trustworthy and effective in the propagation of health messages among their congregants in most African societies (Vincent, Anker & Feeley, 2011). Religions play an important role in the way people perceive, political, social, economic and health issues (Wodka, Fel, Zarzycka, & Kozak, 2022).

The efforts of the Government of Oyo State to control the perennial epidemics of cholera among citizens have been evaluated among health and communication scholars. Studies have shown that people have failed to embrace the efforts of the government to arrest the perennial outbreak of cholera disease in Oyo State in spite of the efforts of its commitment to curtail and minimise the effects of perennial cholera outbreak. Studies have shown that vaccinations against cholera have also suffered as a result of poor and weak awareness campaigns by government and other health stakeholders in Oyo State. Consequently, these call for systematic and empirical investigations.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Know the roles of religious leaders on the adoption of media cholera-related awareness campaigns in Atiba Local Government Area.
2. Ascertain the preferred sources of information about cholera disease among residents of Atiba Local Government Area.
3. Understand the means by which water sanitation and hygiene has minimised the effects of cholera in Atiba Local Government Area.
4. Determine the barriers to media's cholera-related awareness campaigns among people in Atiba Local Government Area of Oyo State.

Review of Relevant Literature

African countries record 25, 000 cases of cholera and more than 350 deaths each time the continent witnesses the outbreak of the disease (Asunduwa, Usman, Isyaku, Shehu, Francis, Balogun & Aworh, 2020). Cholera outbreak remains a public health challenge to most countries in sub-Saharan Africa. Cholera has been endemic in Nigeria since early 1972s when the first cholera disease broke out. It has been a perennial public health issue, not to only Local and State Governments but also Federal Government of Nigeria. Cholera is more endemic in Northern Nigeria than the Southern part of the country due to the issues of hygienic practices and epileptic availability of water supply, as well as issues of open defecation among people. Poor food safety practices among people have also been identified to cause the outbreak of cholera in most endemic areas in Nigeria. Cholera is a vaccine-preventable disease that remains a public health problem in most low- and middle-income nations (Elias, Baltazar, Langa, Baloi, Mboane, Manuel, Assane, Omar, Manso, Capitine, Van Rensburg, Luiz, Mogasale, Marks, Park & Beck, 2022). The outbreak of cholera affects all people irrespective of their ages, with youngest age group mostly impacted by the issue of cholera outbreak. The outbreak of cholera

affects the children under the age of 5 years. Apart from high rate of death arising from cholera outbreak, it causes social and economic disruptions.

Over 700 million people globally still depend on unhygienic and unimproved sources of water for their domestic use. Unclean and unsafe water quality constitute a major factor responsible for the outbreak of cholera disease (Lilje & Mosler, 2018). Cholera is still endemic in Africa and Asia where a large number of people are still very poor and basic provision of social amenities such as public toilets or latrine facilities, including the unavailability and supply of potable water remain a challenge. Studies have shown that apart from the unavailability of water and unhygienic practices, cholera disease is also birthed by acute poverty and over-populated places like internally displaced camps and other overcrowded areas (Sim, 2013). Treatment and WASH campaigns have been poor in most cholera endemic places in Oyo State. Another major factor responsible for the outbreak of cholera disease in many communities in Nigeria is poor and ineffective waste management, including dumping of human faeces in the open within residential places (Monono & Zinyemba, 2023).

Religious leaders can affect the intention to embrace certain health issues in a community. Cholera media campaigns cannot be effective in the absence of religious leaders and other opinion leaders in an African community. Religions provide values, morality, guidance, meaning and significance in the life of the adherents (Rahmi & Putri, 2023). Religion is very important in people's lives and religious leaders are perceived as credible and widely trusted individuals among their sectarian congregants and members (Ali & Ushijima, 2005). Religious leaders occupy a strategic position in African societies, especially when events border on the sharing and communication of health-related issues, explanations and interpretations of government policies to their followers (Kinanggi, Akbar, Muh, & Farid, 2022).

Theoretical Framework

The study is hinged on two-step of information theory. the theory is propounded by Elihu Katz & Paul Lazarfield in the late 1950s. Messages from the mass media, as Aina (2003) maintains, first reach opinion leaders (active-information seekers) who the transmit such messages to friends and community members considered as less active information seekers, who consider them as influential in their community or town. Opinion leaders, such as political leaders, religious leaders, traditional rulers and community leaders, are more exposed to the mass media, and thus, more enlightened than those who are not (Aina, 2003). In most communities in Africa, religious leaders are considered more credible sources of information on socio-economic, political and health issues, and therefore their congregants or subjects embrace, without an iota of doubt, messages that are propagated by religious leaders because of belief and trust reposed in them. This theory explains the study because it directly addresses the influence of religious leaders on the adoption of health message by the people.

Methodology

The study adopted a mixed method. Survey and in-depth interview methods were adopted to guide the study. The two methods were employed to investigate the roles of religious

leaders on the adoption of media's cholera-related awareness campaigns in Atiba Local Government area and to understand the means by which water sanitation and hygiene has minimised the effects of cholera in Atiba Local Government Area. Survey method, as Fink (2009) notes, presupposes the collection of valid information from or about a group of respondents or subjects for the purpose of description, comparison or explanation of their knowledge, attitudes and behaviour. In-depth interview, as in-depth interview is used by researchers to understand the study under investigation from the points of view of the interviewees, to unfold the meaning of the subjects' experiences and to uncover respondents' lived world prior to scientific explanations (Dejonckheere & Vaughn, 2019). In-depth interview method is engaged majorly in health studies to gather qualitative data from relevant subjects on a health issue under investigation (Dejonckheere & Vaughn, 2019).

Atiba Local Government Area comprises ten distinct political wards. There are over seventy areas and communities in Atiba Local Government Area. However, only four are most affected by the incident of cholera disease lately. The areas are Agunpopo, Aremo, Ashipa, Basorun and Ajegunle. Thus, Agunpopo, Aremo, Ashipa, Basorun and Ajegunle were purposively selected for the study because residents of those areas and communities have witnessed the outbreak of the cholera disease directly as victims or indirectly as observants. A purposive sample is the selection of samples on the basis of certain characteristics that are relevant to the study (Andrade, 2021). It is the selection of the samples based on the qualities, features or characteristics they possess that are relevant to the study under investigation. Sample members are selected from well-defined criteria based on the knowledge and expertise of the researchers or investigators (Obilor, 2023). Atiba Local Government Area was divided into ten political wards. Of the ten wards, the most affected areas and communities that are ravaged by the incident of cholera disease were selected. Residents of those areas were presumed to have better knowledge of cholera outbreak either as direct victims or indirect observants in those communities and areas. With the use of simple random sampling, researchers further selected communities and areas that recorded the incident of cholera outbreak in recent times. Thus, Agunpopo, Aremo, Basorun, Ashipa and Ajegunle were selected. A simple random sample is a subset of the population in which every member of the population has an equal chance of selection (Arieska & Herdiani, 2018). Simple random sampling is best suited in homogenous groups and uniformly selected populations.

Convenience sampling was later adopted for the study. A convenience sampling is drawn from a source that is geographically accessible and close to the researchers (Andrade, 2021). Samples are selected based on their availability and accessibility to researchers. Access to all respondents is basically impossible, and thus, respondents are selected on the basis of their geographical locations to the researchers and the respondents' knowledge of the roles of religious leaders on the adoption of media's cholera-related awareness campaigns in Atiba Local Government area, and respondents' understanding of the means by which water sanitation and hygiene has minimised the effects of cholera in Atiba Local Government Area. In-depth interview was adopted because it allowed the researchers to have effective access to the thoughts and opinions of

religious leaders about the roles played by and the influence of religious leaders on the adoption of media cholera-related awareness campaigns in Atiba Local Government Area.

Using Taro Yamane 1967 sample size determination procedure, four hundred respondents were taken in the select areas and communities, including the two major markets in the Local Government Area. Thus, 400 respondents were selected across the communities: Basorun, Agunpopo, Aremo, Ajegunle and Ashipa, as well as Akesan and Ajegunle markets. Questionnaire was used to gather data from the respondents. Two Islamic clerics and two Christian Clerics were purposively selected in the two major mosques and two major churches in Atiba Local Government Area. Thus, Akesan Central Mosque and Agunpopo main Mosque were selected, while Agunpopo Baptist Church and First Baptist Church Isale Oyo were selected. In all, four religious leaders were selected for the study.

The interview session maintained a high confidentiality because the identities of the interview participants were never disclosed due to ethical considerations. Data gathered during the in-depth interview were analysed and interpreted using explanation building and equally analysed thematically in tandem with the objectives of the study. Inferences were made about the respondents' knowledge of the roles of religious leaders on the adoption of media's cholera-related awareness campaigns in Atiba Local Government area and the means by which water sanitation and hygiene has minimised the effects of cholera in Atiba Local Government Area. the unstructured in-depth interview took place in the two different mosques and the two different churches that were selected for the study. The unstructured interviews enabled the researchers and the respondents or subjects to seamlessly ask and answer questions as the events unfold during the interview. Of the 400 copies of questionnaire administered on the respondents, 395 copies of the questionnaire were returned and found useful for the study. The researchers made use of two research assistants who helped in the administration of the questions in the study areas.

Results

Qualitative Data from the In-Depth Interview Reports

Theme 1: Roles of Religious Leaders on the Media's Cholera Related Awareness Campaigns

Data from the in-depth interview showed different roles of religious leaders on the adoption of Media's Cholera related awareness campaigns. The discussions revealed that religious leaders are very influential in the adoption of media's cholera-related awareness campaigns on radio because religious leaders are more trusted and have higher credibility. Providing more insights about the roles of religious leaders on the adoption of media's cholera-related awareness campaigns, a cleric at First Baptist Church Isale Oyo, said:

We are the custodians of religious ethos. Apart from the traditional rulers who have some measures of influence on cultural and traditional matters in their communities, we are more respected among opinion leaders in African societies. In fact, some communities respect, value and revere their religious leaders more than their traditional rulers. These features and more enable us to influence our religious followers or congregants on any issue. People embrace, with all their hearts, every message that is passed through us. During community-based health campaigns, people do not embrace such health initiatives until we are co-opted to persuade our followers and congregants to embrace the message. Therefore, we are seen to be more credible and trusted more than any other community-based opinion leaders because people believe we are stewards of Almighty God on earth. It may even interest you to know that when a certain health programme is disseminated either on radio or television, people come here to seek for our opinions and advice on the issue. Many women have come here to get education about child-spacing, polio immunisation among others.

Another interviewee, the Chief Imam of Basorun Central Mosque, maintained that:

Many people have so much trust in us. I have used my *Imamship* to influence the lives of many in so many positive ways. We have intervened in government-centred policies and other health-related programmes in this community and brought enlightenment to *Jammah* about those policies or health issues. During polio immunisation programmes, health officials from the State Ministry of Health and the ones at the Atiba Local Government Area come to solicit for our support and assistance to make sure that parents bring out their children for polio immunisation programmes. So, during *Jummat* on Friday, we usually encourage and persuade the parents to embrace the health interventions. One issue we have found is that when we enlighten our male members about election, policies of government, health programme, budget, and many more, we discover that people embrace such programme more because men are the heads of the family.

Theme 2: Barriers to Media's Cholera-Related Awareness Campaigns among People

Data from the in-depth interview showed different barriers to media's cholera-related awareness campaigns. The discussions revealed that weak surveillance system for early detection of cholera and illiteracy on the part of the people are the barriers to media's cholera-related awareness campaigns. Providing more insights about the barriers to media's cholera-related awareness campaigns among people, the Chief Imam of Central Mosque Akesan in Oyo, said:

It is some of us who interact daily with people and offer different kinds of advice to them that understand their mental, psychological and even health needs. Many of them are barely able to understand simple directive and advice. The high level of illiteracy among them is a barrier to any developmental messages embarked upon by government, local, national or international agency. During COVID-19 in this place, all manner of fake information was being spread about the disease. It took the advisory intervention of religious leaders like me for them to go for COVID-19 drugs and vaccinations in our hospitals. However, other issue that strengthens the spread of cholera disease in this community is the weak surveillance system to detect the disease early so that its spread can be arrested on time. Surveillance and early detection system is very weak in Atiba Local Government Area because there are no cholera outbreak situation room where it can be reported immediately people witness its outbreak. Apart from this, people prefer not to even report, but to make use of local herbs to treat the disease whenever it breaks out.

Another interviewee, the Reverend of Agunpopo Baptist Church, said that: Most religious leaders face one challenge or the other when certain health programme is to be diffused in this community. Of course, you, as a religious leader, are to encourage them to embrace cholera-related messages on radio. However, the adoption or embrace of such media's cholera-related messages greatly depends on socio-economic and cultural factors. Some families do not believe in the use of foreign -manufactured drugs instead, they prefer herbal medicine to cure any ailment. Other families among them may be disposed to using foreign-manufactured drugs but lack monetary muscles to effect the purchase. The educational attainment of most of the members is very poor, hence they do not see the need to embrace cholera-related awareness campaigns whenever such is announced during church activities.

Survey Data

Table 1: Preferred Sources of Information about Cholera Disease among Residents

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Use of Megaphones	116	29.4%
Religious Leaders	155	39.2%
Radio Broadcasts	67	17%
Family Sources	57	14.4%
Total	395	100

Source: Researchers' Fieldwork, 2025

Table 1 shows that 116 respondents representing 29.4% maintained that the use of megaphones are the preferred sources of information about cholera disease among

residents of Atiba Local Government Area, 155 respondents representing 39.9% averred that religious leaders the preferred sources of information about cholera disease among residents of Atiba Local Government Area, 67 respondents representing 17% affirmed that radio broadcasts are the most preferred sources of information about cholera disease among residents of Atiba Local Government Area, while 57 respondents representing 14.4% maintained that family sources are the preferred sources of information about cholera disease among residents of Atiba Local Government Area of Oyo State.

Table 2: Means by Which Water Sanitation and Hygiene have minimised the Effects of Cholera

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Sustained Commitment of the Policy Makers	41	10.4%
Community Engagement and Mobilisation	152	38.5%
Craetion of Rapid Response Teams	68	17.2%
Widespread Hygiene Education	134	33.8%
Total	395	100

Table 2 shows that 41 respondents representing 10.4% stated that sustained commitment of the policy-makers are means by which water sanitation and hygiene have minimised the effects of cholera in Atiba Local Government Area, 152 respondents representing 38.5% maintained that community engagement and mobilisation are the means by which water sanitation and hygiene have minimised the effects of cholera, 68 respondents representing 17.2% averred that creation of rapid response teams are the means by which water sanitation and hygiene have minimised the effects of cholera, while 134 respondents representing 33.8% affirmed that widespread hygiene education activities are the means by which water sanitation and hygiene have minimised the effects of cholera in Atiba Local Government Area of Oyo State.

Discussion

Findings showed that religious leaders are very influential in the adoption of media cholera-related awareness campaigns on radio because religious leaders are more trusted and have higher credibility. The findings agree to the positions of Oktavianus & Dewi (2023) who found that the voice of religious leaders is respected in their communities during health interventions by government. Religious leaders have the influence on their followers, and therefore, they can influence their followers to oppose or accept certain health messages initiated by government, local or foreign agencies (Oktavianus & Dewi, 2023).

Findings further showed that weak surveillance system for early detection of cholera and illiteracy on the part of the people are the barriers to media's cholera-related awareness campaigns. The findings are in sync with the positions of Igere, Okoh & Nwodo (2020) who found that cholera endemic-regions are usually occupied with people of poor educational backgrounds and weak socio-economic status, who have little or no knowledge about hygienic practices. Also, Igere *et al* (2020) aver that timely

interventions, control, investigations and surveillance by government and health agencies are largely lacking in most cholera-endemic areas in Africa.

Findings showed that religious leaders the preferred sources of information about cholera disease among residents of Atiba Local Government Area. the findings are in sync with the submissions of IkaPurnamasari (2020) who found that religious leaders are charismatic figures and have special power that can influence the actions of the people who are their followers or congregants. Messages, either good or bad, that are delivered by religious leaders are strictly followed by their followers and congregants IkaPurnamasari (2020). Also, the findings are in tandem with the positions of Zahrah & Damayanti (2023) who found that religious leaders are social agents who are crucial in the dissemination of health-related messages to their members and congregants.

Findings showed that community engagement and mobilisation have minimised the effects of cholera through water sanitation and hygienic practices. The findings align with the findings of Sebert, Kuhlmann, Altman & Galavotti (2016) who found that community engagement, participation, mobilisation and engagement are important components of any achievable health-related programmes in developing nations. Also, engaging members of the communities as actors and participants in the health enlightenment campaigns has reduced the perennial outbreak of cholera disease in most African societies (Dada, Cocoman, Portela, De Brún, Bhattacharyya, Tunçalp, Jackson & Gilmore, 2023).

Conclusion and Recommendations

In the conception and execution of health-related messages and programmes, the roles of religious leaders are very germane. Unlike the media of communication that are urban-centric and disseminate health-related messages to the people in the urban centres, religious leaders must be used for health-related information such as cholera awareness programmes and knowledge in local communities. Much credibility is attached to any health-related message like cholera awareness campaign, disseminated by religious leaders, and thus, it is more accepted in the local communities. Establishment of emergency cholera treatment centres across Atiba Local Government Area with a view to arresting and treating the cases of perennial outbreak of the disease on time will help minimise death rates arising from the cholera disease in most local communities in Atiba Local Government Area, and by extension, Oyo State and Nigeria.

People embrace health-related messages emanating from religious leaders because the position they occupy in our society. Inclusion of religious leaders in the communication policies of the Federal Government of Nigeria and Oyo State Government has become imperative. The positive perception of religious leaders in the community-based communication process has made their inclusion in evitable in the communication of health-related messages in local communities in Nigeria and Africa by extension. Access to drinking and clean water is critical to put a stop to the perennial cases of cholera disease in Atiba Local Government Area of Oyo State. Women, men, young boys and girls must be made to participate in the initiation anti-cholera campaigns, prevention, management and control to fight against perennial cases of cholera disease in local communities in Atiba Local Government Area and even urban centres.

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